

A study of errors and misconceptions in mathematics at elementary school stage

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Abstract: The main purpose of this study was to study the errors and misconceptions in mathematics by the elementary school students. Three-Tier Concept Achievement Test in Mathematics (TTCATM) comprising of 50 items was administered to 1000 sixth-grade students. After the identification of errors and prior to the identification of misconceptions, false negatives and lack of knowledge were observed in between. In addition, the analysis of data showed that location and gender did not have significant effect. Patterns and sources of errors and misconceptions were also identified.

Keywords: Errors, Misconceptions, Mathematics, Elementary School Stage, TTCATM

1 Introduction

The National Policy on Education (1986) has suggested that 'Mathematics should be envisaged as the vehicle to train a student to think about, purpose, scrutinize and to eloquent logically. Apart from being a definite subject it should be associated to any subject connecting analysis and reasoning'.

At the elementary stage, students get the first taste of the power of Mathematics through the application of powerful abstract concepts that compress previous learning and experience. This enables them to revise and consolidate basic concepts and skills learnt at the primary stage, which is essential from the point of view of achieving universal mathematical literacy. Therefore, elementary school stage is a significant period in students' mathematical development, a period in which they develop the capacity to understand and use mathematical knowledge. The concept formation developed during this period prepares platform for higher levels of education. This is also a point in students' learning in which misconceptions are born and if gone unnoticed, these can continue with a student into secondary school and cause confusion when new concepts are built upon elementary school foundations. However, like an ailment, if caught early these misconceptions can be treated and students' mathematical understanding can be reconstructed.

Mathematics education is based on problem-solving, application of knowledge and manipulations and when the students meet word-problems; their non-systematical and incomplete knowledge cause faults and conceptual mistakes. Generally when developing the problems, analyzing the problems, explaining the results and confirming processes aren't comprehended well, students go away from creativeness and are directed to learn by heart. Students learn by trying to fit what they are taught to their own worlds. They exhibit large differences in their ability to grasp and understand mathematical concepts. This mismatch between the levels of pupils thinking and the intellectual demand of the subject-matter causes misconceptions in Mathematics. Diagnostic tests assess all the errors as misconceptions. But, all the errors are not misconceptions, since misconceptions happen when a person shows confidence in the objectively false concept (Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia, 2008). Errors may be due to mistakes, false negatives, lack of knowledge and misconceptions among students (Eryilmaz and Surmeli, 2002; Pesman, 2005 and Kutuluay, 2005). Error is a deviation from

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accuracy or correctness and taken as wrong answers given to the objective type test items (first-tier) of three-tier tests. Misconceptions are false conceptions and can be assessed in three-tier tests by referring to incorrect answer in first-tier, incorrect reasoning in second-tier and confidence shown by the student in third-tier.

General achievement test attempts to assess students' performance in school subjects in terms of single score and the test does not identify specific errors and weaknesses etc. Although, criterion referenced tests are very helpful in identifying the misconceptions of the students but their effectiveness is doubted as students do not justify their answers. To overcome this problem two-tier tests were used (Odom et al., 1995; Cataloglu, 2002 and Tan et al. 2002). The researchers also found that two-tier tests also overestimate the proportions of the misconceptions. In two-tier tests, the students are not asked for their confidence about their answers. The three-tier concept achievement test (Eryilmaz and Surmeli, 2002; Pesman, 2005 and Kutuluay, 2005) that asks the students to show their confidence about the answers given in the first two tiers has the ability to assess students' performance in the subject, errors committed by students in the test (wrong answers in the first tier), false negatives and to differentiate misconceptions from lack of knowledge as the sources of errors.

The review of studies conducted by Sharma 1981; Dixit 1985; Phalachandra 1989; Reap and Cavallo 1992; and Aseema and Gakhar 2004 support the fact that females underachieve in Mathematics in relation to males. While the result of some studies showed that males underachieve in relation to females in various subjects (Misra 1986; Rosaly 1992; and Steinmayr and Spinath 2008), whereas various studies showed that males and females do not differ with regard to Mathematics achievement (Barua 1981; Kohle 1985; Kaul et al. 2000; Gupta 2001; Misra 2003; and Klein et al. 2010). Pandey 1981; Puri 1984; Kohle 1985; Misra 1986; Chand 2002; Aseema and Gakhar 2004; Mehra 2004; Mather 1994; and Judson and Nishimori 2005 found urban atmosphere because of it has more facilities more conducive to better Mathematics achievement than a rural environment. Therefore, in order to select for the best effective, appropriate and suitable teaching method, it is very important to identify the differences between rural and urban, male and female elementary school students in Mathematics on TTCATM in terms of errors, misconception, false negatives and lack of knowledge (misconception wise).

2 Objectives of the Study

1. To study the difference between male and female elementary school students in terms of dimensions of errors and misconceptions in Mathematics on TTCATM.
2. To study the difference between rural and urban elementary school students in terms of dimensions of errors and misconceptions in Mathematics on TTCATM.
3. To study the patterns of errors and misconceptions on TTCATM among elementary school students.
4. To identify the sources of errors and misconceptions of elementary school students in Mathematics.
5. To suggest remedies for clearing misconceptions of the elementary school students and rectifying errors in Mathematics.

3 Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between male and female elementary school students in terms of dimensions of errors and misconceptions in Mathematics on TTCATM.
2. There is no significant difference between rural and urban elementary school students in terms of dimensions of errors and misconceptions in Mathematics on TTCATM.

4 Method & Sample

Considering the nature of the problem under investigation descriptive survey method of research was used. All the 6th class students who are studying in government elementary, high and senior secondary schools of Punjab were the target population in the present study. Multi-stage sampling was employed for the selection of sample for the study. 1000 students from 44 schools comprised the sample for present study, which includes equal number of male & female (500) students and rural & urban students (500). Further, 332 students based on their performance on TTCATM comprising equal number of high and low achiever boys and girls from urban and rural area were selected for interview.

5 Tool for the research

Standardized TTCATM for 6th class comprising of 50 items having criterion validity, content validity and 0.69 reliability coefficient was used to study the dimensions of errors and misconceptions of elementary school students. Each item comprises of three tiers. First tiers of the test items are ordinary objective type questions. Second tiers include a set of reasons for the answers on the first tiers. Third tiers questions if examinees are confident about their answers for the first two tiers. Moreover, blank alternatives to write any suggestion different from choices are added at the end of second tiers of each item. Choice selections indicating misconceptions and confidence are awarded one and zero other wise. Error, false negative, lack of knowledge and misconception is identified if a student scores one in first tier; one in first tier and zero in second tier; one in first two tiers and zero in the third tier; and one in each tier respectively. For Example:

Question	
a. A triangle with angles of measure 30°, 70°, 80° is called an acute angled triangle.	True/False
b. Because:	
(i) One angle is acute.	()
(ii) Two angles are acute.	()
(iii) Three angles are acute.	()
(iv) Any other _____	
c. Are you confident?	Yes/No

Student got 1 mark for answer 'False' in 1st tier, 1 mark for answer 'One angle is acute' in 2nd tier, 1 mark for answer 'Yes' in the 3rd tier and 0 otherwise. Error, false negative, lack of knowledge and misconception is identified if a student scores one in first tier; one in first tier and zero in second tier; one in first two tiers and zero in the third tier; and one in each tier respectively.

6 Data Collection

The researcher personally visited the schools and collected data from 6th class students on TTCATM. Further, the data was also collected through interviews with students in order to gain a deeper understanding of the patterns and sources of students' responses to TTCATM.

7 Analysis and Statistical Treatment of Data

Chi-square test of hypothesis of independence (difference) was used to analyze the data. The results of analysis of data on eight content areas: 1. Ray, 2. Line, 3. Line –Segment, 4. Angle, 5. Pairs of Angles, 6. Transversal and Pairs of Angles, 7. Parallel Lines and Pairs of Angles made by Transversal and 8. Triangles are shown in the Table 1 and Table 2:

Table 1 Difference between Male and Female Elementary School Students in terms of Dimensions of Errors and Misconceptions in Mathematics on TTCATM.

Content		N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Chi-Square Value
Errors	Male	500	205	292	278	247	238	166	244	249	0.64
	Female	500	209	287	266	247	241	165	255	245	
Misconceptions	Male	500	49	102	105	75	63	57	74	60	1.00
	Female	500	52	91	107	74	66	58	78	57	
False Negative	Male	500	134	169	130	144	139	97	144	169	1.28
	Female	500	140	171	116	147	138	95	153	170	
Lack of Knowledge	Male	500	21	21	44	28	35	11	26	20	1.05
	Female	500	17	25	43	26	37	12	24	19	

df = 7, Table value = 14.07

Table 2 Difference between Rural and Urban Elementary School Students in terms of Dimensions of Errors and Misconceptions in Mathematics on TTCATM

Content		N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Chi-Square Value
Errors	Urban	500	212	284	263	248	239	166	245	246	1.22
	Rural	500	202	294	281	246	240	165	253	248	
Misconceptions	Urban	500	52	98	107	76	64	62	76	57	0.80
	Rural	500	50	94	105	73	64	54	76	60	
False Negative	Urban	500	145	166	115	147	138	95	145	170	2.52
	Rural	500	128	174	131	144	139	98	151	169	
Lack of Knowledge	Urban	500	15	20	42	25	37	10	24	20	3.82
	Rural	500	24	26	45	29	36	13	26	19	

df = 7, Table value = 14.07

From Table 1 and Table 2, it is clear that calculated value of chi-square is less than the table value of chi-square for significance at .05 level and with df = 7. Hence we accept the both hypotheses.

Thus, we can conclude that there is no significant difference between rural and urban; male and female elementary school students in terms of dimensions of errors and misconceptions in Mathematics on TTCATM.

8 Main Findings & Conclusion

1. On the content area 'Ray', students had committed errors, false negatives, lack of knowledge and misconceptions on an average of 41.37%, 27.37%, 3.87% and 10.13% respectively.
2. On the content area 'Line', students had committed errors, false negatives, lack of knowledge and misconceptions on an average of 57.80%, 34%, 4.60% and 19.20% respectively.
3. On the content area 'Line-Segment', students had committed errors, false negatives, lack of knowledge and misconceptions on an average of 54.35%, 24.55%, 8.65% and 21.15% respectively.
4. On the content area 'Angle', students had committed errors, false negatives, lack of knowledge and misconceptions on an average of 49.39%, 29.10%, 5.36% and 14.93% respectively.
5. On the content area 'Pairs of Angles', students had committed errors, false negatives, lack of knowledge and misconceptions on an average of 47.85%, 27.73%, 7.25% and 12.88% respectively.
6. On the content area 'Transversal and Pairs of Angles', students had committed errors, false negatives, lack of knowledge and misconceptions on an average of 33.10%, 19.23%, 2.30% and 11.57% respectively.
7. On the content area 'Parallel Lines and Pairs of Angles made by Transversal', students had committed errors, false negatives, lack of knowledge and misconceptions on an average of 49.80%, 29.65%, 5 % and 15.15% respectively.
8. On the content area 'Triangle', students had committed errors, false negatives, lack of knowledge and misconceptions on an average of 49.38%, 33.86%, 3.89% and 11.63% respectively.
9. Students had difficulty in identifying line. Students strongly hold the misconception that a line has end-points.
10. Many students had difficulty in identifying line-segment in a complex figure. Students also strongly hold the misconception that a line-segment has no end point.
11. Students had difficulty in identifying complete angle. Students also had difficulty in understanding the concept of acute angle, right angle, straight angle and reflexive angle. Some students had difficulty in differentiating obtuse angle from reflex angle.
12. Students strongly hold the misconceptions that angle means common initial point of rays regardless the number of rays and an angle of measure 270° is a reflexive angle.
13. Students also strongly hold the misconceptions that adjacent angles are those who are nearer to each other; a pair of vertically opposite angles is formed by angles which are opposite to each other; two angles form a pair of complimentary angles only if both of them are acute; in a pair of supplementary angles one of them is always acute and other is always obtuse.

14. Students also strongly hold the misconception that a line is a transversal if it intersects parallel lines at distinct points.
15. Students strongly hold the misconception that parallel lines are those which are intersected by a transversal. Some students holds the misconceptions that sum of interior angles on the same side of the transversal is always 180° .
16. Students also strongly hold the misconception that pairs of corresponding angles are always equal and pairs of alternate interior angles are always equal.
17. Students strongly hold the misconceptions that a triangle divides the plane into four parts: interior, exterior, triangle and triangular region; an equilateral triangle has no side different.
18. Students also strongly hold the misconception that if in a triangle one angle is acute it is an acute angled triangle.
19. Patterns of errors and misconceptions were entry level, concept achievement level, perception level and application level.
20. The errors results mainly due to mistakes, lack of knowledge and misconceptions.
21. Some common sources of misconceptions i.e. confusion, language impression, overgeneralization, misclassification, misidentification, lack of previous knowledge, oversimplification and teaching-learning activities were found between students.

9 Further Suggestions

In the light of the findings of the present study, following are some suggestions that can be used by teachers to improve the Mathematics education:

1. Teachers and curriculum developers should take students' misconceptions and alternative ideas into consideration and design remedial techniques to improve learning.
2. A teacher should focus on students' cognitive level to eliminate misconceptions. The major focus of instructions should be on creating links between concrete experiences and abstract concepts.
3. The teaching practitioners should use a variety of teaching methods and combination of them to bridge the gap between errors and misconceptions.
4. Teachers should use three-tier tests over multiple-choice tests and two tier tests to investigate the misconceptions of the students.
5. Teachers can use the TTCATM for formative evaluation to assess the misconceptions of the sixth class students about the geometrical concepts.
6. Text book editors can include activities for experimentation in Mathematics laboratory, more examples, non-examples and simple questions dealing with the misconceptions instead of complex situations and questions.

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